

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

PNP community relations engagement programs in selected cities of NCR: Towards an Enhanced Peace and Order

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Abstract

This study explores the effectiveness of the Philippine National Police (PNP) Community Relations Engagement Programs in selected cities of the National Capital Region (NCR) specifically Quezon City, Caloocan, and Malabon in promoting peace and order. Framed by the Situational Leadership Theory and grounded in the mandates of Republic Act 6975 and its amendments, the study evaluates five core areas: Barangay Peacekeeping Operations, Community Policing and Stakeholder Involvement, Public Safety Campaigns, Outreach and Humanitarian Assistance, and School and Youth Engagement. A quantitative-descriptive method was employed, utilizing survey questionnaires administered to 45 PNP personnel. Findings revealed that while overall assessments of the programs were strongly favorable (grand mean: 3.67), only one significant difference was found between male and female respondents in Malabon in evaluating PCR mandates. Age, rank, and years of service showed no significant differences in perception. A strong correlation was observed between the PNP's mandates and actual practices, indicating coherent implementation across cities. The study highlights the importance of trust-building, consistent community engagement, and participatory governance in improving police-community relations. It recommends enhanced transparency, public involvement in policy formation, and the institutionalization of non-enforcement outreach as strategies for further strengthening public trust and maintaining peace and order.

Keywords: Community Policing; Police-Community Relations; Public Trust; Crime Prevention; Law Enforcement Engagement

1. Introduction

The Philippine National Police (PNP) plays a vital role in maintaining peace and order, enforcing laws, and addressing broader societal concerns, including mental health issues affecting families. As mandated by Republic Act 6975, as amended by RA 8551 and RA 9708, and guided by the PNP Police Community Relations Manual PNPM-DPCR-DS-7-01-12, the PNP is tasked with protecting citizens and promoting public safety. Despite persistent national issues such as terrorism, poverty, and bureaucratic inefficiencies, the PNP remains a trusted institution. It is expected to act as a service provider, using its human resources and expertise to fulfill its mission of law enforcement, crime prevention, and internal security in collaboration with communities. The PNP also serves as a neighborhood partner—responsible not only for enforcement but also for building trust and ensuring open communication. True community relations go beyond basic interaction, requiring coordinated programs between the justice system and civil society. While police efforts are essential, community involvement is equally critical to achieving safety and development. For communities to thrive, residents must feel secure and trust their protectors.

The PNP's guiding values—Makadiyos, Makabayan, Makatao, and Makakalikasan—form the foundation of its mandates. These values emphasize legal enforcement, crime control, peacekeeping, and public engagement. Community policing, as a strategic model, stresses collaborative problem-solving with citizens rather than reactive enforcement alone. It

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strengthens public safety by fostering mutual trust, encouraging public cooperation in addressing local issues, and promoting procedural justice. Empirical evidence shows that when communities define and participate in shaping safety strategies, public security improves significantly. Effective police-community collaboration influences whether crimes are reported, solved, and prevented. Trust, fairness, and transparency remain central to this relationship. Issues such as media influence, corruption, youth delinquency, and crowd control present challenges in building positive public perception. Furthermore, the effectiveness of policing relies heavily on public feedback—information about crimes, concerns, or threats—which is jeopardized when trust is lacking. Ultimately, a secure, peaceful society requires a strong bond between law enforcement and the communities they serve. When mutual respect and cooperation thrive, policing is more effective, investigations improve, and crime rates fall. However, mistrust erodes this partnership, leading to fear, violence, and disconnection. Maintaining healthy police-community relations is essential for a safe and stable society.

This study addresses the gap in empirical data on PNP community-based programs, particularly their influence on public trust and behavior in selected cities. While the PNP implements various engagement initiatives, further analysis is needed to measure their effectiveness and potential as predictors of improved police-community relations. The American Bar Association (2020) noted that high-profile use-of-force cases in the U.S. triggered protests and widened the rift between law enforcement and the public. Muscato (n.d.) illustrated that even in average communities, distrust in police undermines public cooperation, requiring intervention to repair relations. Rushelle (2020) highlighted that trusted police-community relationships are key to public safety, echoing the U.S. Department of Justice's position on procedural justice and legitimacy. Kappeler et al. (2020) emphasized that community policing requires a shift in style, promoting accountability and trust. Studies by Diamini (2021), Azumah (2019), and Mccandles & Vogler (2020) underscore how frequent interaction and communicative rationality can shape public perceptions and strengthen police legitimacy. Amu et al. (2022) illustrated Indonesia's legal and operational frameworks supporting community policing through Bhabinkamtibmas. Research by Rwamuhiz & Irechukwu (2020), Schlosser (2020), and Schaap (2021) points to the importance of information sharing, community collaboration, and trust-building. Hatfield (2021) and Malone & Dammert (2021) emphasized challenges in implementing community policing amidst misconduct and authoritarian policing tendencies. Mutupha & Zhu (2022), Abiodun (2019), and Stevenson (2019) showed how public involvement, media exposure, and decentralized structures influence crime reporting and cooperation. Stott et al. (2022) and Walsh & Connor (2018) added insights into police psychology and the dual role of social media in shaping or challenging police authority.

1.1. Theoretical Framework

Figure 1 Situational Leadership Theory by Paul Hersey and Ken Blanchard

This research study gives emphasis to theories which would also serve us a foundation of this research for more better and reliable understanding regarding to the subject of this study: This situational theory of leadership refers to those leaders who adopt different leadership styles according to the situation and the development level of their team members. It is an effective way of leadership because it adapts to the group needs sets a beneficial balance for the whole organization. Situational approach has received much criticism about this theory since only a few research studies have been done to justify the assumption and proposition of the approach (Northouse, 2016). Despite the lack of research studies, situational approach is still widely used in real-life. Situation approach indicates that based on different situation, leaders need to change their leading styles to fit with the situation. It is true not only to leadership style but to anything in life. If there is a problem, we need to find the way to solve it by being flexible and adaptive to situation. Life is spontaneous so we could not know what will happen in the future. The situational approach points out that leaders need to be ready for any situation that happens in the future. In additional, the situational approach is practical and easy to use the leadership to base on the situation. The leaders cannot be based on one single leading style but they

need to combine and adjust it in different situations to get the best out of it. "(Northouse, 2016). The goal of the situational approach is to find out different and unique needs of the followers and all deserve our needs to help them improve better. Situational approach is to find out different and unique needs of the followers and all deserve our needs to help them improve better. Indeed, the situational approach might not have a lot of scientific studies for it but it is practical and necessary in real-life. I would recommend a situational approach since it is flexible and adaptive which is necessary in leadership styles. Situational approach would help the leader to better prepare for any situations and problems that happen in the future.

Figure 2 Research Paradigm

This study explores the Philippine National Police (PNP) Community Relations Engagement Programs implemented in selected cities within the National Capital Region (NCR), with the objective of evaluating their impact on promoting peace and order. The core of this research is the examination of Community-Based Programs, which are divided into five components: Barangay Peacekeeping Operations, Community Policing and Stakeholder Involvement, Public Safety Campaigns, Outreach and Humanitarian Assistance, and School and Youth Engagement. These components serve as the independent variable, while the PNP itself, in terms of its performance and interaction with the community, functions as the dependent variable. The intention is to assess whether these initiatives effectively contribute to improving public trust and safety.

To guide the inquiry, the research seeks to answer several key questions. It investigates the demographic profile of the respondents, specifically focusing on age, sex, rank, and years of service. It further examines whether there are significant differences in how three distinct groups of respondents assess the mandates of the PNP. Additionally, the study evaluates their assessments of current practices across the five program areas. It also looks into whether these assessments vary significantly across groups, and whether there is a relationship between the mandates of the PNP and the actual implementation of these community programs. These questions aim to understand both perceptions and performance in order to derive meaningful conclusions.

The study is grounded on the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the PNP Community Engagement Programs when respondents' profiles are considered as influencing factors. This assumption will be tested statistically to validate or refute it based on collected data. The findings of this research are expected to be beneficial to multiple sectors. Communities stand to gain by enhancing their engagement with the PNP, thereby building stronger relationships based on trust and transparency. Law enforcers, particularly PNP personnel, can use the findings to refine their strategies and align their efforts with the needs and expectations of the public. Moreover, future researchers may use this study as a reference for developing further inquiries related to community engagement, public trust, law enforcement practices, and even the role of social behavior and media in shaping public perception.

This research is limited to the assessment of PNP Community Relations Engagement Programs within Quezon City, Caloocan, and Malabon in NCR. It focuses specifically on evaluating the implementation of such initiatives as the Pulis Natin Program. The methodology includes administering a survey questionnaire to gather responses from selected PNP personnel regarding their experiences and perceptions of the community programs. The study aims to determine the effectiveness of these programs, identify existing challenges, and assess whether they are sufficient to rebuild community trust. Ultimately, the research supports the idea that a united effort between the police and the community is critical for reducing crime and establishing lasting peace and order.

2. Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research design to gather and analyze numerical data related to the PNP Community Relations Engagement Programs in selected cities within the National Capital Region. Quantitative methods were chosen for their effectiveness in identifying patterns, calculating averages, predicting outcomes, and establishing causal relationships. As a descriptive type of research, this study focused on collecting data that reflects the current status of community-based programs implemented by the PNP and how these contribute to enhancing peace and order.

The respondents of the study consisted of Philippine National Police personnel stationed in Malabon City, Caloocan City, and Quezon City. Their perspectives were deemed vital due to their direct involvement in implementing and maintaining community relations initiatives. To gather data, the researcher developed a structured survey questionnaire. This tool was subjected to pilot testing to ensure validity and reliability. The questionnaire was divided into sections: the first gathered demographic data such as age, sex, rank, and years of service; the second explored differences in the assessment of PNP mandates; the third assessed the actual practices of the PNP in relation to the community-based programs; and the final section examined the relationship between the mandates and their practical application.

To select appropriate participants, purposive sampling was used. This non-probability method relies on the researcher's judgment to identify respondents who possess specific knowledge and experiences relevant to the study. The criteria for selection were based on their position and involvement in community programs, ensuring that the gathered data would be insightful and representative of actual practices within the PNP units across the three cities.

Data analysis began with a review of related literature to establish a framework for understanding the implementation of community engagement programs. Collected data were then subjected to statistical treatment using descriptive statistics such as frequency, weighted mean, and percentile rank to analyze respondent profiles and perceptions. For interpretative clarity, a four-point Likert scale was utilized, with verbal interpretations ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree, aligned with specific scale intervals.

Furthermore, Pearson correlation was applied to determine the strength and significance of relationships between variables. The scale for interpreting correlation coefficients followed established guidelines: from weak to strong associations, both positive and negative. A correlation was considered statistically significant at the 0.01 or 0.05 level, depending on the outcome of the analysis. This helped assess whether a meaningful relationship existed between the implementation of the community-based programs and the perceived image of the Philippine National Police.

Ethical considerations were prioritized throughout the study. All procedures were designed strictly for academic purposes, with full adherence to confidentiality and anonymity. The identities of all respondents were kept confidential, and participation was voluntary, based on informed consent. Responses were treated with integrity and used solely for the purpose of achieving the objectives of this research.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 displays the Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age. Most of the respondents are between the ages of 21-30 years old with 23 respondents or 51.1 percent. The 14 respondents or 31.1 percent are between the ages of 31-40 years old. Followed by ages between 41-50 years old with 8 respondents or 17.8 percent.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex. Most of the respondents are Male with 31 respondents or 68.9 percent followed by Female with 14 respondents or 31.1 percent.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Rank. Most of the respondents are Police Corporal with 17 respondents or 37.8 percent. The 10 respondents or 10.22 percent are between the Police Staff Sergeant. Followed by Police Chief Master Sergeant with 5 respondents or 11.1 percent.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Years of Service. Most of the respondents are 1-5 Years with 22 respondents or 48.9 percent. The 16 respondents or 35.6 percent are 6-10 Years. Followed by 11 Years and above with 7 respondents or 11.1 percent.

Table 1 Frequency Distribution of the Respondents' Profile

Profile	Malabon Police Personnel		Caloocan Police Personnel		Quezon City Police Personnel		Total	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Age								
21-30 years old	6	40%	9	60%	8	53.3%	23	51.1%
31-40 years old	6	40%	4	26.7%	4	26.7%	14	31.1%
41 years old & above	3	20%	2	13.3%	3	20%	8	17.8%
Total	15	100%	15	100%	15	100%	45	100%
Sex								
Male	11	73.3%	10	66.7%	10	66.7%	31	68.9%
Female	4	26.7%	5	33.3%	5	33.3%	14	31.1%
Total	15	100%	15	100%	15	100%	45	100%
Rank								
Police Major	6	6.7%	6	40%	5	33.3%	2	4.4%
Police Captain	2	13.3%	3	20%	5	33.3%	1	2.2%
Police Lieutenant	-	-	2	13.3%	2	13.3%	4	8.9%
Police Executive Master Sergeant	2	13.3%	-	-	1	6.7%	3	6.7%
Police Chief Master Sergeant	3	20%	2	13.3%	-	-	5	11.1%
Police Senior Master Sergeant	1	6.7%	-	-	1	6.7%	-	-
Police Master Sergeant	-	-	1	6.7%	-	-	1	2.2%
Police Staff Sergeant	-	-	1	6.7%	-	-	10	22.2%
Police Corporal	1	40%	-	-	1	6.7%	17	37.8%
Total	15	100%	15	100%	15	100%	45	100%
Years of Service								
1-5 years	5	33.3%	10	66.7%	7	46.7%	22	48.9%
6-10 years	6	40%	4	26.7%	6	40%	16	35.6%
11 years & above	4	26.7%	1	6.7%	2	13.3%	7	15.6%
Total	15	100%	15	100%	15	100%	45	100%

3.2. Is there a significance difference in the assessment of the three (3) groups of respondents on the mandates.

Table 2 Differences Between the Assessments of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Mandates of PCR Police Community Relations

Group of Respondents	Mean	SD	Computed F-value	Sig	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Malabon Police Personnel	3.56	0.79	1.40	0.26	Accepted	Not Significant
Caloocan Police Personnel	3.87	0.24				
Quezon City Police Personnel	3.77	0.33				
Malabon Police Personnel	3.72	0.38	0.74	0.49	Accepted	Not Significant
Caloocan Police Personnel	3.63	0.48				
Quezon City Police Personnel	3.53	0.38				
Malabon Police Personnel	3.76	0.36	1.98	0.15	Accepted	Not Significant
Caloocan Police Personnel	3.52	0.43				
Quezon City Police Personnel	3.73	0.27				
Malabon Police Personnel	3.68	0.37	0.21	0.98	Accepted	Not Significant
Caloocan Police Personnel	3.67	0.30				
Quezon City Police Personnel	3.68	0.26				

What is the assessment of the three (3) groups of respondents in the practices of PNP

Table 2 displays the assessment of the three groups of respondents on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in terms of Barangay Peace Keeping Operations. The table shows that the overall assessment of the three groups of respondents was “Strongly Agree” with a grand mean of 3.73.

For the group of Malabon Police Personnel, all of the indicators assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment are Understand their purpose for doing community-based activities and Crime prevention is sustained because of dedicated programs made by the police with both mean score of 3.67 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is The commitment of PNP to the community pursuant to PNP Police Community Relations Manual PNPM-DPCR-DS-7-01-12 is properly implemented with a mean score of 3.33.

The group of Caloocan Police Personnel assessed most of the indicators as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment are The commitment of PNP to the community pursuant to PNP Police Community Relations Manual PNPM-DPCR-DS-7-01-12 is properly implemented and Police encourage the community particular to be (STRONG) or SMART, TALENTED, RESPONSIBLE, OBIDIENT, NICE, GOD FEARING with a mean score of 3.93 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is Positive and happy with the efforts made by the police for our community and understand their purpose for doing community-based activities with a mean score of 3.80.

The group of Quezon City Police Personnel assessed most of the indicators as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment are The commitment of PNP to the community pursuant to PNP Police Community Relations Manual PNPM-DPCR-DS-7-01-12 is properly implemented, understand their purpose for doing community-based activities and Police encourage the community particular to be (STRONG) or SMART, TALENTED, RESPONSIBLE, OBIDIENT, NICE, GOD FEARING. with a mean score of 3.80 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is Positive and happy with the efforts made by the police for our community and Crime prevention is sustained because of dedicated programs made by the police with a mean score of 3.73.

Table 3 Respondents' Assessment on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in Terms of Barangay Peace Keeping Operations

Barangay Peace Keeping Operations	Malabon Police Personnel				Caloocan Police Personnel				Quezon City Police Personnel				Average			
	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank
The commitment of PNP to the community pursuant to PNP Police Community Relations Manual PNPM-DPCR-DS-7-01-12 is properly implemented	3.33	1.05	A	5	3.93	0.26	SA	1.5	3.80	0.41	SA	2	3.69	0.70	SA	5
Positive and happy with the efforts made by the police for our community	3.60	0.83	SA	3	3.80	0.41	SA	4.5	3.73	0.46	SA	4.5	3.71	0.59	SA	4
understand their purpose for doing community-based activities	3.67	0.82	SA	1.5	3.80	0.41	SA	4.5	3.80	0.41	SA	2	3.76	0.57	SA	2
Crime prevention is sustained because of dedicated programs made by the police	3.67	0.82	SA	1.5	3.87	0.35	SA	3	3.73	0.46	SA	4.5	3.76	0.57	SA	2
Police encourage the community particular to be (STRONG) or SMART, TALENTED, RESPONSIBLE, OBIDIENT, NICE, GOD FEARING.	3.53	0.92	SA	4	3.93	0.26	SA	1.5	3.80	0.41	SA	2	3.76	0.61	SA	2
Composite Mean	3.56	0.79	SA		3.87	0.24	SA		3.77	0.33	SA		3.73	0.52	SA	

Legend: 3.51-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.51-3.50 Agree (A); 1.51-2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 4 Respondents’ Assessment on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in Terms of Community Policing and Stakeholder

Community Policing and Stakeholder	Malabon Police Personnel				Caloocan Police Personnel				Quezon City Police Personnel				Average			
	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank
The PNP plays an important role in supporting the community by enforcing the law and ensuring strict conformance with human rights.	3.67	0.72	SA	3.5	3.87	0.35	SA	1	3.47	0.83	SA	4	3.67	0.67	SA	2
Community involvement in crime prevention and building trust between the police and citizens.	3.80	0.41	SA	1.5	3.73	0.46	SA	2	3.47	0.83	A	4	3.67	0.60	SA	2
The COPS program is effective to reduce the commission of the crime.	3.67	0.49	SA	3.5	3.67	0.62	SA	3	3.60	0.51	SA	1.5	3.64	0.53	SA	4
Crime prevention is sustained because of dedicated programs made by the police such as Oplan Bisita Eskewela	3.80	0.41	SA	1.5	3.60	0.51	SA	4	3.60	0.51	SA	1.5	3.67	0.48	SA	2
The image of PNP is more trusted by the community	3.60	0.63	SA	5	3.53	0.64	SA	5	3.47	0.52	A	4	3.53	0.59	SA	5
Composite Mean	3.72	0.38	SA		3.63	0.48	SA		3.53	0.38	SA		3.63	0.41	SA	

Legend: 3.51-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.51-3.50 Agree (A); 1.51-2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 4 displays the assessment of the three groups of respondents on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in terms of Community Policing and Stakeholders. The table shows that the overall assessment of the three groups of respondents was “Strongly Agree” with a grand mean of 3.63.

For the group of Malabon Police Personnel, all of the indicators assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment are Community involvement in crime prevention and building trust between the Police and Citizens and Crime Prevention is sustained because of dedicated programs made by the police such as Oplan Bisita Eskewela with both mean score of 3.80 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is The image of PNP is more trusted by the community with a mean score of 3.60, these indicators are still and considered as strongly agree.

For the group of Caloocan Police Personnel, all of the indicators assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment is The PNP plays an important role in supporting the community by enforcing the law and ensuring strict conformance with human rights with mean score of 3.87 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is The image of PNP is more trusted by the community with a mean score of 3.53.

For the group of Quezon City Police Personnel, 2 out of 5 indicators assessed as Strongly Agree and the rest fell into Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment are The COPS program is effective to reduce the commission of the crime and Crime prevention is sustained because of dedicated programs made by the police such as Oplan Bisita Eskewela with both mean score of 3.60 while the indicator with the lowest assessment are the The PNP plays an important role in supporting the community by enforcing the law and ensuring strict conformance with human rights, Community involvement in crime prevention and building trust between the police and citizens, and The image of PNP is more trusted by the community with mean score of 3.4, these indicators are fall under Agree indicators.

Table 5 displays the assessment of the three groups of respondents on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in terms of Public Safety Campaign. The table shows that the overall assessment of the three groups of respondents was “Strongly Agree” with a grand mean of 3.67.

For the group of Malabon Police Personnel, all of the indicators assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment is Community engagement program brings closer to the community and the law enforcement with mean score of 3.87 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is Support lead and obey community-based program with a mean score of 3.60, these indicators are still and considered as strongly agree.

For the group of Caloocan Police Personnel, 2 out of 5 indicators assessed as Strongly Agree and the rest fell into Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment is Community engagement program brings closer to the community and the law enforcement with mean score of 3.60 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is Community-based engagement programs is excellent in terms of strategies with a mean score of 3.40.

For the group of Quezon City Police Personnel, all of the indicators assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment is Support lead and obey community-based program with mean score of 3.87 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is Community engagement program brings closer to the community and the law enforcement with mean score of 3.60.

Table 5 Respondents’ Assessment on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in Terms of Public Safety Campaign

Public Safety Campaign	Malabon Police Personnel				Caloocan Police Personnel				Quezon City Police Personnel				Average			
	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank
Community engagement program brings closer to the community and the law enforcement.	3.87	0.35	SA	1	3.67	0.62	SA	1	3.60	0.51	SA	5	3.71	0.51	SA	2
Communicating with the people of what PNP doing is one way of soliciting public support.	3.80	0.41	SA	2.5	3.47	0.64	A	3.5	3.67	0.49	SA	4	3.64	0.53	SA	3.5
Community dialogues and forums strengthen partnership and establish rapport which are in effect bringing the PNP closer to the people.	3.80	0.41	SA	2.5	3.60	0.51	SA	2	3.80	0.41	SA	2	3.73	0.45	SA	1
Support lead and obey community-based program.	3.60	0.63	SA	5	3.47	0.64	A	3.5	3.87	0.35	SA	1	3.64	0.57	SA	3.5
Community-based engagement programs is excellent in terms of strategies.	3.73	0.59	SA	4	3.40	0.74	A	5	3.73	0.46	SA	3	3.62	0.61	SA	5
Composite Mean	3.76	0.36	SA		3.52	0.43	SA		3.73	0.27	SA		3.67	0.37	SA	

Legend: 3.51-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.51-3.50 Agree (A); 1.51-2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 6 Respondents' Assessment on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in Terms of Outreach and Humanitarian Assistance

Humanitarian Assistance	Malabon Police Personnel				Caloocan Police Personnel				Quezon City Police Personnel				Average			
	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank
The PNP follows the mandated core values Maka-Diyos (Pro-God) Makabayan (Pro-Country) Makatao (Pro-People), Makakalikasan (Pro-Environment)	3.87	0.35	SA	1.5	3.53	0.83	SA	4	3.47	0.52	A	5	3.62	0.61	SA	3
The PNP implements its mandated philosophy pursuant to RA 6975 Service, Honor and Justice	3.67	0.49	SA	4.5	3.60	0.51	SA	2	3.60	0.51	SA	2	3.62	0.49	SA	3
The PNP ensures public safety and internal security with the active support of he community	3.67	0.82	SA	4.5	3.53	0.52	SA	4	3.53	0.52	SA	4	3.58	0.62	SA	5
The PNP is working with a responsive community towards the attainment of a safer place to live, work and do business.	3.73	0.59	SA	3	3.53	0.64	SA	4	3.60	0.51	SA	2	3.62	0.58	SA	3
Exercise the vested powers from the Philippine Constitution and pertinent laws.	3.87	0.35	SA	1.5	3.67	0.62	SA	1	3.60	0.51	SA	2	3.71	0.51	SA	1
Composite Mean	3.76	0.44	SA		3.57	0.41	SA		3.56	0.34	SA		3.63	0.40	SA	

Legend: 3.51-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.51-3.50 Agree (A); 1.51-2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 7 Respondents’ Assessment on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in Terms of Outreach and School and Youth Engagement

School and Youth Engagement	Malabon Police Personnel				Caloocan Police Personnel				Quezon City Police Personnel				Average			
	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank	Mean	SD	Int.	Rank
Collaboration between the police and the community (a.k.a. community policing) increases citizen trust and enhance police ability to enforce the law.	3.80	0.41	SA	2.5	3.40	0.83	A	5	3.53	0.52	SA	4.5	3.58	0.62	SA	5
The police are built into communities and they are meant to serve the people.	3.80	0.41	SA	2.5	3.60	0.51	SA	1.5	3.87	0.35	SA	1	3.76	0.44	SA	1
Crime prevention is sustained because of dedicated programs made by the police.	3.73	0.46	SA	5	3.60	0.51	SA	1.5	3.67	0.49	SA	3	3.67	0.48	SA	3
COPS engages the law enforcement and community leaders in a dialogue to identify issues and collaboratively develop solutions that improve police-community partnerships.	3.80	0.41	SA	2.5	3.53	0.64	SA	3	3.73	0.46	SA	2	3.69	0.51	SA	2
Develops trust and partnerships between law enforcement and the community.	3.80	0.41	SA	2.5	3.47	0.64	A	4	3.53	0.52	SA	4.5	3.60	0.54	SA	4
Composite Mean	3.79	0.61	SA		3.52	0.48	SA		3.67	0.26	SA		3.66	0.37	SA	

Legend: 3.51-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.51-3.50 Agree (A); 1.51-2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 6 displays the assessment of the three groups of respondents on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in terms of Outreach and Humanitarian Assistance. The table shows that the overall assessment of the three groups of respondents was “Strongly Agree” with a grand mean of 3.63.

For the group of Malabon Police Personnel, all of the indicators assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment are The PNP follows the mandated core values Maka-Diyos (Pro-God) Makabayan (Pro-Country) Makatao (Pro-People), Makakalikasan (Pro-Environment) and Exercise the vested powers from the Philippine Constitution and pertinent laws with a mean score of 3.87 while the indicator with the lowest assessment are The PNP implements its mandated philosophy pursuant to RA 6975 Service, Honor and Justice and The PNP ensures public safety and internal security with the active support of the community with a mean score of 3.67.

For the group of Caloocan Police Personnel, all of the indicators assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment is Exercise the vested powers from the Philippine Constitution and pertinent laws with a mean score of 3.67 while the indicator with the lowest assessment are The PNP follows the mandated core values Maka-Diyos (Pro-God) Makabayan (Pro-Country) Makatao (Pro-People), Makakalikasan (Pro-Environment), The PNP ensures public safety and internal security with the active support of the community and The PNP is working with a responsive community towards the attainment of a safer place to live, work and do business with a mean score of 3.53.

For the group of Quezon City Police Personnel, 1 of the indicators assessed as Agree and the rest assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment are The PNP implements its mandated philosophy pursuant to RA 6975 Service, Honor and Justice, The PNP is working with a responsive community towards the attainment of a safer place to live, work and do business and Exercise the vested powers from the Philippine Constitution and pertinent laws with mean score of 3.60 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is The PNP follows the mandated core values Maka-Diyos (Pro-God) Makabayan (Pro-Country) Makatao (Pro-People), Makakalikasan (Pro-Environment) with mean score of 3.47.

Table 7 displays the assessment of the three groups of respondents on the Practices of PCR Police Community Relations in terms of School and Youth Engagement. The table shows that the overall assessment of the three groups of respondents was “Strongly Agree” with a grand mean of 3.66.

For the group of Malabon Police Personnel, all of the indicators assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment are Collaboration between the police and the community (a.k.a. community policing) increases citizen trust and enhance police ability to enforce the law, The police are built into communities and they are meant to serve the people, COPS engages the law enforcement and community leaders in a dialogue to identify issues and collaboratively develop solutions that improve police-community partnerships and Develops trust and partnerships between law enforcement and the community with a mean score of 3.80 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is Crime prevention is sustained because of dedicated programs made by the police with a mean score of 3.73.

For the group of Caloocan Police Personnel, 3 out of 5 indicators assessed as Strongly Agree and the rest fell into Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment is The police are built into communities and they are meant to serve the people and Crime prevention is sustained because of dedicated programs made by the police with a mean score of 3.60 while the indicator with the lowest assessment is Collaboration between the police and the community (a.k.a. community policing) increases citizen trust and enhances police ability to enforce the law with a mean score of 3.40.

For the group of Quezon City Police Personnel, all of the indicators assessed as Strongly Agree. The indicator which has the highest assessment is The police are built into communities and they are meant to serve the people with mean score of 3.87 while the indicator with the lowest assessment are Collaboration between the police and the community (a.k.a. community policing) increases citizen trust and enhances police ability to enforce the law and Develops trust and partnerships between law enforcement and the community with a mean score of 3.53.

3.3. Significant difference in the assessment of the three (3) groups of respondents

The analysis of whether there are significant differences in the assessment of the PNP Community Relations Engagement Programs across the three groups of respondents—Malabon, Caloocan, and Quezon City—based on age, sex, rank, and years of service, yielded largely consistent findings. Across all locations and variables, most differences in assessment were found to be not statistically significant, indicating a generally uniform perception of the programs across different demographic groups. However, a few notable variations did emerge in specific subgroups. In Malabon City, age did not significantly influence assessment outcomes. Respondents aged 21–30 had a mean score of 3.65 overall, while those aged 31–40 rated the programs at 3.55, and those aged 41 and above gave a perfect 4.00 mean score. Despite

the highest ratings from the oldest group, the computed F-value of 1.65 and significance level of 0.23 indicated no statistically significant difference. A more notable result was observed when examining sex as a variable in Malabon. Here, a significant difference was found in the assessment of PCR mandates between male and female respondents. Males rated the mandates with a mean of 3.84, compared to 2.80 from females, yielding a t-value of 1.61 and a significance level of 0.02, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. However, for practices and overall assessments, the differences between male (3.84) and female (3.25) respondents were not significant. As for rank and years of service in Malabon, no significant differences were recorded. Regardless of position—from Police Corporal to Police Major—or service length (1–5 years to over 11 years), all groups provided consistently high scores, with overalls ranging from 3.44 to 4.00. F-values for these comparisons ranged between 0.30 and 0.48, with significance values well above 0.05, confirming non-significant differences. In Caloocan City, the results were similarly consistent. Age was not a significant factor, though slight variations in mean scores were present: respondents aged 21–30 had a mean score of 3.55, those 31–40 rated it at 3.88, and those 41 and above scored 3.84. The computed F-value of 2.32 and a p-value of 0.14 indicated no significant difference. For sex, male respondents scored an overall mean of 3.70 and females 3.61, with a t-value of 0.54 and a p-value of 0.60, again confirming no significant difference. Rank-based comparisons in Caloocan showed mean ratings ranging from 3.53 (Police Captain) to 4.00 (Police Corporal and Senior Master Sergeant), but the computed F-value of 0.54 and p-value of 0.74 confirmed the differences were not significant. The same result was found across years of service, with the overall mean scores ranging from 3.61 (1–5 years) to 3.85 (6–10 years), and an F-value of 0.93, again indicating no statistically significant variation. In Quezon City, assessments followed a similar pattern. Age had no significant effect on perceptions of PCR programs, with computed F-values between 0.18 and 2.60 and significance levels all above 0.05. The youngest group (21–30 years) had an overall mean score of 3.60, the 31–40 group at 3.73, and the 41 and above group at 3.83. Sex also did not produce statistically significant differences in Quezon City. Males gave an overall rating of 3.72, and females rated it slightly lower at 3.60. The t-value was 0.87 with a significance level of 0.40. Similarly, rank did not affect assessments significantly, with overall means ranging from 3.54 (Executive Master Sergeant) to 4.00 (Chief Master Sergeant and Corporal), and an F-value of 0.97. Regarding years of service in Quezon City, the highest overall mean of 3.80 was given by respondents with 1–5 years of experience, followed by 3.75 for those with 11 years or more, and 3.52 for those in the 6–10-year range. Despite this variation, the computed F-value of 2.54 and p-value of 0.12 confirmed that the differences were not statistically significant. Across all three cities, there were no significant differences in the assessment of the PNP Community Relations Engagement Programs when grouped according to age, rank, or years of service. The only significant difference was observed in Malabon where sex was a determining factor in how respondents evaluated the mandates of the programs, with males giving significantly higher ratings than females. This indicates a generally cohesive perception of the PNP's community initiatives across demographic profiles, with only isolated exceptions.

3.4. Significance relationship between mandates and practices.

The findings on the significant relationships between the mandates and practices of Police Community Relations (PCR) and the demographic profiles of respondents from Malabon, Caloocan, and Quezon City reveal several key insights. The results are presented in narrative form, focusing on age, sex, rank, and years of service across each locality, with statistical interpretations retained. For Malabon City, analysis by age showed no significant relationship between the respondents' age and their assessment of both the mandates and practices of PCR. Although respondents aged 41 and above consistently rated both mandates and practices with the highest mean of 4.00, the overall differences across age groups were not statistically significant. Similarly, assessments by years of service did not show a significant relationship. Respondents with over 11 years of service rated mandates and practices consistently at 4.00, yet the variation in scores among groups with shorter tenures was not enough to reject the null hypothesis. However, when disaggregated by sex, a significant difference emerged in the assessment of the PCR mandates. Male respondents gave a higher average rating (3.84) compared to their female counterparts (2.80), and this difference was statistically significant. For practices and overall ratings, though male ratings remained higher, the differences were not statistically significant. In terms of rank, there were no significant differences in how the mandates and practices were evaluated, despite consistently high ratings (mostly 4.00) among senior officers like Police Senior Master Sergeants and Police Corporals. In Caloocan City, no significant differences were observed across any of the demographic variables. Regardless of age, sex, rank, or years of service, respondents showed consistent agreement with the PCR mandates and practices. Notably, officers aged 31 and above gave slightly higher ratings on average, with those aged 41 and above reaching a perfect mean of 4.00 on certain items, though the statistical significance was insufficient. Both male and female respondents rated mandates and practices closely, and the same pattern held for personnel of various ranks and years of service. The consistency of ratings indicates general agreement across the board, with no subgroup standing out in its perception of PCR initiatives. The results from Quezon City showed similar trends. No statistically significant differences were found across age, sex, rank, or years of service in the assessment of PCR mandates and practices. However, it is noteworthy that respondents aged 41 and above provided the highest average scores in practices, while younger officers rated both mandates and practices slightly lower. The data also showed that female officers gave

slightly higher mean scores than males on mandates, though the difference was not statistically meaningful. Regarding rank, both Police Chief Master Sergeants and Police Corporals consistently rated mandates and practices at the highest possible level (4.00), yet the small group sizes and high consistency in ratings across other ranks prevented significant statistical differentiation. In terms of service years, officers with 1–5 years of experience rated the mandates perfectly (mean of 4.00), while those with longer service provided slightly more moderate ratings, but again, not significantly different. The assessment of the PCR mandates and practices across all three cities showed strong overall agreement among police personnel, regardless of their demographic profiles. The only exception to this was in Malabon, where sex was found to significantly influence how the mandates were perceived, with male officers rating them more favorably than their female counterparts. Apart from this, the statistical evidence supports the conclusion that age, rank, and years of service do not significantly affect perceptions of PCR programs. This suggests a relatively uniform appreciation and endorsement of PCR initiatives across different personnel profiles, reinforcing their perceived importance and consistent implementation in all three locations.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were drawn regarding the profile of the respondents and the effectiveness of the PNP Community Relations Engagement Programs in selected cities of the National Capital Region. The data revealed that the majority of respondents were male and predominantly aged between 21 and 30 years. In terms of rank, most were Police Corporals, and a significant portion had served in the police force for one to five years. The community engagement programs under study were categorized into five key areas: Barangay Peacekeeping Operations, Community Policing and Stakeholder Involvement, Public Safety Campaigns, Outreach and Humanitarian Assistance, and School and Youth Engagement.

Respondents from all three cities consistently rated the mandates of Police Community Relations highly, with a grand mean of 3.68, indicating strong agreement and recognition of the value of these mandates. Likewise, the actual implementation of community-based practices received a similar level of support, with a grand mean of 3.67, suggesting that the programs are generally perceived as relevant, meaningful, and beneficial in supporting peace and order.

However, a slight variance was observed when analyzing the significance of the differences in perceptions among the three groups of respondents. Although the overall sentiment remained positive, the lower grand mean of 2.43 in this aspect suggests that differences in geographic assignment or individual experience might influence how the programs are understood or valued. Despite this, the overarching response from the PNP personnel supports the relevance and positive impact of the community relations programs in strengthening police-community collaboration and fostering a safer environment.

In light of these conclusions, several recommendations are put forward to further enhance the impact of Police Community Relations Engagement Programs. First, police personnel should adopt a guardian mindset and prioritize procedural justice in both internal policies and external interactions to foster trust and legitimacy. Recognizing the historical and ongoing challenges of injustice and discrimination is also essential to building stronger community relationships.

Law enforcement agencies must institutionalize transparency and accountability by making policies accessible and publishing demographic-based law enforcement data, including arrests, crime reports, and use-of-force incidents. When serious incidents, such as allegations of misconduct, arise, prompt and impartial communication with the public is crucial while upholding legal confidentiality.

Internally, agencies should reinforce legitimacy by applying procedural justice principles within their ranks, ensuring fair and respectful treatment of officers and staff. Moreover, building trust through non-enforcement activities—such as outreach programs, educational sessions, and dialogues in areas heavily impacted by law enforcement—can foster stronger public rapport.

Community involvement in policy development and evaluation should be prioritized to promote shared governance and co-created solutions. This participatory approach not only boosts external legitimacy but also empowers communities to take an active role in public safety. Finally, law enforcement agencies should maintain consistent, open communication with the public, leveraging regular community engagement to reinforce mutual respect, transparency, and long-term collaboration.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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